

IMPROVING LEGAL MECHANISMS TO COUNTER CORRUPTION IN SPORTS

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Abstract: the article characterizes issues of criminal liability for corruption in the field of sports and measures aimed at resolving problems and improving legal mechanisms for combating corruption existing in the field of sports relations at the current stage of development of society and the state.

Key words: criminal liability, sports relations, public danger, corruption, punishment.

The fight against corruption in the new Uzbekistan is one of the priority areas of state policy defined in the Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan. In it, along with ensuring the rule of law and further reform of the judicial and legal system, one of the most important tasks is defined as improving the organizational and legal mechanisms for combating corruption and increasing the effectiveness of anti-corruption measures[1]. And as the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev rightly emphasizes in this regard, it is necessary to inoculate society with the “vaccine of honesty”, since corruption in its various manifestations hinders the development of the country. And if we do not eradicate this vicious phenomenon, we will not be able to create a truly favorable business and investment climate, not a single sphere of life in our society will develop and, as a result, raising the fight against corruption to a qualitatively and quantitatively new level is a product of today's political will[2].

It should be noted that the reforms currently being carried out in the area of combating corruption are yielding effective results. The republic has created legal foundations, adopted conceptually significant normative legal acts aimed at preventing corruption. These include: the Law “On Combating Corruption”, the Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On additional measures to improve the system of combating corruption in the Republic of Uzbekistan”, State programs covering all state and public organizations, and events carried out on a national scale[3,4,5].The fight against corruption is carried out in conjunction with the implementation of international

experience and relevant legal norms into the legislation and practice of the country. In particular, the establishment of the Anti-Corruption Agency is an example of the implementation in the country of the relevant articles of the UN Convention against Corruption, ratified by Uzbekistan, as well as the “Jakarta Principles” in international anti-corruption practice. The National Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan for Combating Corruption and its territorial councils were also created, and the Openbudget portal was launched –“Open budget” for the implementation of public control over the regulation of budget expenditures, reporting on violations of budget legislation and organizing procedures for making proposals to improve the budget process. In order to eliminate administrative and bureaucratic barriers, simplify and increase the efficiency of registration, licensing and permit issuance procedures, State Service Centers, People's and Virtual Reception Offices of the President, a "Helpline", as well as "helplines", "virtual reception offices" of ministries and government departments have been created in all regions, The practice of conducting "visiting receptions" of government officials at all levels has been established in order to ensure the rights and freedoms of citizens. In the fight against corruption, the process of widespread implementation of the "compliance control" system in government agencies and economic entities is underway[6,7,8].

Currently, state support for physical culture and sports is one of the most important areas of the socio-economic policy of our state. Within the framework of the fifth direction of the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, it is envisaged that in order to protect public health, broad conditions will be created for protecting public health and an important task will remain the development of physical culture and sports, the promotion of a healthy lifestyle.

In this regard, the current stage of development of sports relations, associated with the deepening of market relations and liberalization of the economy, the development of entrepreneurial relations has brought about major changes in the legal regulation of sports relations, in the organizational structure of physical culture and sports management, in the sources of their financing, the legal status of athletes and coaches, new trends in the impact of legal means on sports relations were revealed, thereby changing the place of physical culture and sports in the system of social values.

The progress of physical culture and sports relations in our country is very dynamic, which, in turn, requires constant attention to improving the regulatory framework, creating fundamentally new legislative acts that consolidate both the achievements of physical culture and sports in our country and the shortcomings that arise in this area of public relations[9].

Thus, in Uzbekistan in 2019-2023, 30 players and referees, 8 coaches, 7 heads of football clubs, 2 employees of the administration of football clubs, a total of 77 athletes, were found to be involved in fixed matches. Moreover, there are cases of illegal receipt of material assets or property benefits by participants and organizers of sports competitions, as well as bribery of participants and organizers of sports competitions.

Back in his speech in August 2021, the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, at a meeting with athletes and coaches who participated in the XXXII Summer Olympic Games, spoke about corruption in sports: "The level of national championships has decreased. The most alarming cases are corruption in this area. For example, it has become commonplace to register the same athletes of certain categories for participation in the republican stage of the competition without holding regional stages. Therefore, there are very few strong athletes at our championships and almost no competition. In addition, teams from the regions are underrepresented in team sports tournaments."

Based on the objectives set by Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the ceremony of presenting the international anti-corruption award; in order to prevent such situations, the issue of criminal liability is currently being considered in legislation. The Criminal Code should be supplemented with relevant articles establishing criminal liability for the illegal acquisition of material assets or property interests by participants and organizers of sports competitions, as well as for bribery of participants and organizers of sports competitions.

The draft law "On Amendments to the Criminal Code for the Purpose of Preventing Corruption in the Sphere of Sports", containing these procedures, will serve to improve national legislation taking into account modern international standards and advanced foreign experience, and to form an uncompromising attitude towards corruption in the sphere of sports, ensuring the inevitability of responsibility for all and raising Uzbekistan's position in international rankings. As a result, zero tolerance for corruption will be formed in this sector, and the inevitability of responsibility will be ensured[10,11,12].

In addition, in order to successfully implement tasks in the field of sports, the need is dictated for further improvement of public administration in this area, the system of holding competitions in team sports, digitalization of work on identifying, selecting and selecting talented young athletes in the regions and organizing championships of Uzbekistan, which, in turn, will serve to create a fair system for attracting athletes to national teams in Olympic sports.

Current issues of legal regulation of sports relations both in national and foreign law have been the subject of close attention of many authors for a long time. The problems of

legal regulation and the impact of criminal law norms on sports relations in national and foreign law are the object of increased scientific interest among authors from the CIS countries. Therefore, taking into account the similarity of legal systems, the similarity of problems faced by the legal development of these states, as well as the preferential development of external relations within the CIS, the scientific developments of scientists from the Commonwealth countries are of great scientific interest. In this regard, the study of the causes that give rise to problems associated with relations in the field of physical culture and sports, the study and analysis of criminal liability of subjects in the field of sports, characteristics of offenses established by legislation on physical culture and sports and the measures of responsibility applied for their commission, resolution of problems existing in the sphere of sports relations at the current stage of development of society and the state, is an indisputable and urgent task of criminal law science, requiring proper theoretical understanding aimed at forming an adequate legal framework and which will serve as a valuable contribution to the further improvement of sports legislation.

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International Law, Business and Political Science Journal

ISSN-L 3235-9799

E-ISSN 3235-9799

IF(Impact Factor)13.24

<https://journallaw.totalh.net/>
Volume: 5. Issue 6 May 2025